

A Snapshot Analysis of Bengali Muslim Writers' Contribution to India's Independence

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Abstract

This article explores those Bengali Muslim writers, renowned or not, who contributed to the Independence of India anyhow. It analyses their writings or activities in the light of the anti-British spirit between the late nineteenth century and the early twentieth century. This exploratory research is grounded in the theory of decolonization. It also focuses on the roles of chosen Bengali Muslim women writers like Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain, and Razia Khatun Chaudhurani along with the roles of select Bengali male literary figures like Kazi Nazrul Islam, Mir Mosharraf Hossain, Muhammad Shahidullah, Mohammad Akram Khan, Abul Kalam Shamsuddin, Ismail Hossain Siraji, Mohammad Mozammel Huq, Wazed Ali, Rezaul Karim, and Muzaffar Ahmed. This study also sheds light on national movements, Hindu-Muslim unity, women's emancipation, anti-imperialist idealism, *Zamindari system*, literary organizations, colonial resistance, literary pursuit, and independence. It aims to unveil how Muslim literary personalities from Bengal with their relentlessly brave attempts create national consciousness and anti-British sentiment among the masses, and motivate Indians, especially Bengali Indians to unite and fight against the British colonial force to achieve India's long-cherished freedom.

Keywords: Bengali, Muslim, Writers, India, Independence, decolonization.

Prominent Indian statesmen, authors, and journalists collaborated to defeat the colonial hegemony and win India's independence. Indians owe a great deal to notable Bengali nationalists like Rabindranath Tagore, Bagha Jatin, Bankim Chandra Chatterjee, Bipin Chandra Pal, Chittaranjan Das, Khudiram Bose, and Subhas Chandra Bose. Some notable Bengali Muslim freedom fighters are "Sirajul Haq, Hamidul Haq, Abdul

Momin, Maksuddin Ahmad, Maulvi Gha Kader, Wali Nawaz, Ismail, Zahiruddin, Chand Miyan, Altaf Ali, Alimuddin, and Fazlul Kader Chowdhury” who held arms alongside Hindus (Stella 62). Eminent Bengali Muslim literary figures like Kazi Nazrul Islam, Mir Mosharraf Hossain, Muhammad Shahidullah, Mohammad Akram Khan, Abul Kalam Shamsuddin, Ismail Hossain Siraji, Mohammad Mozammel Huq, Wazed Ali, Rezaul Karim, Muzaffar Ahmed, Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain, and Razia Khatun Chaudhurani were instrumental in the historic Indian Independence movement. Bengali Muslim writers’ chief aim is to plant the seeds of awareness principally in the minds of Hindus and Muslims during the white reign (British Empire) in India. They diagnosed the religious cultural diversity between two religious communities and endeavour to unite them. They came to the revelation that Hindu-Muslims’ combined strength can take India to the most awaited destination which is the freedom of India. They also revealed that the English people attempted to divide the Indians by anyhow. Some Bengali Muslim writers participated, in physicality, in Indian freedom movements and some others penned to create national consciousness among all and awareness for unity. As per the view of Jawaharlal Nehru, “the first and dominant urge” is to achieve the freedom of India (44). Muslim writers in Bengal joined political parties and became a part of some literary organizations.

To cease Hindu-Muslim disharmony, Mir Mosharraf Hossain (1848-1911), a renowned Muslim writer from Bengal, wrote *Go-Jiban* published in 1889 and here, he questions the eating beef of Muslims, for which court a case was registered against him. He argues that eating the flesh of cow is not obligatory as per Muslim religious book. He held that “the indiscriminate slaughtering of cows would endanger agriculture and accordingly, wrote the essay '*Gokul Nirmul Ashanka*', against this practice” (Mir Mossaraf). One of the Land Revenue Systems introduced by the British government is *Zamindari* System. It was a trick of Lord Cornwallis to gain more money from land resulting in hard times of the peasants in Bengal along with Orissa, Vanarasi, and Bihar after the initiation of this oppressive mechanism in 1793. Mr Hossain understood this problem and raised his voice against this system in his book, *Zamindar Darpan* (1873) which was set “against the background of the peasant riots in Sirajganj during 1872-73”

(Mir Mossaraf). His autobiographical novel, *Udasin Pathiker Maner Katha* (1890), talks about the history of the indigo movement in 1859 in Bengal. It encompasses the collision between a female *Zaminder* and a British indigo planter. It also demonstrates how an indigo planter tortures and oppresses the indigo peasants. Bengali Muslim Marxist poet, Kazi Nazrul Islam (1899-1976) is truly acclaimed as the rebel poet worldwide. His poems, songs, essays, articles, and other writings foster a sense of national consciousness in the minds of Indians. He combats the Hindu-Muslim antagonism in his poem “*Kandari Husiyar*” to unite the two communities against British sovereignty. His poem, “*Hindu-Musalman*” gives the message of communal tolerance. Some of his revolutionary works in verse are “*Agniveena*” (Lyre of Fire) published in 1922, ‘*Bisher Bashi*’ (Flute of Poison) in 1924, and ‘*Bhangar Gaan*’ (The Song of Annihilation) in 1924; they influenced different anti-British uprisings for the independence of India. His poem, “*Bidrohi*” (The Rebel) published in the literary magazine, *Moslem Bharat* in 1922, gives a tremendous impetus to the revolutionaries of India, during the non-cooperation movement led by Mahatma Gandhi. His other notable rebellious poems are “*Dhumketu*” (The Comet), “*Karar Oi Louho Kopat*”, and “*Pralayollas*” (Destructive Euphoria). As his pen goes against the British government, he is imprisoned but, his writings did not cease to continue anyway in jail too. Nazrul joined the British Indian army in the 49 Bengal Regiment in 1917. His joining the army is a protest to the fact that the British government hesitates to “entrust Bengalis as a fighting force” (Chandan). In 1920 while staying in Kolkata in the office of *Bangiya Muslim Sahitya Samiti*, he came in contact with the communist politician and journalist Muzaffar Ahmad who allowed Nazrul to be involved in political affairs. In 1921 he corporeally intervened in the Indian non-cooperation movement. In the procession of the non-cooperation movement he sang “*Viksha dao! Viksha dao!*” (Give alms! Give alms); he wanted to awaken the Indians against the nasty colonial business to emancipate India. A united strength is imperative irrespective of religion, caste, and gender to fight the colonial force. Women’s participation along with men in the Indian independence movement can strengthen doubly the resistance against the British. In this regard, some Bengali Muslim writers raise questions about gender disparity. Kazi Nazrul Islam sings

for gender equality. Bengali Muslim female writers like Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain, Azizunnesa Khatun, Akhtar Mahal Syeda Khatun, Mrs. Masuda Rahman, Nurunnesa Khatun Vidyavinodini, Razia Khatun Chaudhurani, Musammat Sahifa Banu, and Shamsunnahar Mahmud demand women's rights to education and emancipation through their writings in colonial Bengal. Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain (1880-1932) was a celebrated Bengali Muslim woman writer. Her *Motichur Volume 2* (1922) is a set of essays – “Nurse Nelly”, “*Gyanfal*” (The Fruit of Knowledge), “*Sristi Tawtho*” (The Theory of Creation), and “*Nari-Srihsti*” (The Creation of Women). In the essay “Nurse Nelly”, she criticizes the colonial missionary education that opposes indigenous education disdainfully. She highlights the significance of a grassroots movement and argues in favour of developing an educational system free from colonial influence (Hakeem 52). She chastises the English missionary ladies who prey on vulnerable minds in her society and opposes “imbibing British values (Hakeem 52). She stresses that women's education is a key factor in molding women to be strong enough to “stand side by side with Indian men to overthrow British rule” (Hakeem 52). Razia Khatun Chaudhurani (1907-34) was a Bengali Muslim poet, short story writer and essayist. She is a Bengali Muslim writer who participated in Indian national struggles. Saika Hossain claims that Razia was perhaps one of the few female authors, who was able to closely observe the politics of the day due to her participation in the Khilafat and Swadeshi movements. (273). Her short story “Sramik” is an example of her political commentary. Muhammad Shahidullah (1885-1969), a Muslim writer from Bengal by learning Sanskrit as the first Muslim teaches a lesson of communal harmony to the Hindus and Muslims during the colonial era. He was convinced that by fostering the spirit of Bengali nationalism, Hindus and Muslims could transcend their differences in religion (Sajen). The creation of a national literature would be the main objective in order to achieve that (Sajen). One of the renowned leaders of the Khilafat Movement was Maulana Muhammad Ali Jauhar who supported Shahidullah's initiative of learning Sanskrit at Calcutta University when the professors of the Sanskrit Department “could not accept the idea of teaching a Muslim the holy book, *Veda*” (Sajen). While it is hoped that more Muslim academics will study Sanskrit than there are currently, he expressed

confidence that instances like the "Shahidullah Affair," in which a pundit at Calcutta University refused to teach Sanskrit to a Muslim student, would not happen again. (Sajen). Mohammad Yakub Ali (1888-1940) was a Bengali Muslim literary figure who participated in national politics. He was part of the Khilafat and Non-cooperation movements. As a result, he was imprisoned by the colonial government. His confinement destroyed his teaching career and he became a member of Bangiya Mussalman Sahitya Samiti (1911). Mohammad Akram Khan, (1868-1968) was a Bengali literary personality, journalist, and political figure, who took birth in the district, 24 Parganas of West Bengal. The British government arrested Mr Khan for his publication of the periodical *Sebak* which was banned for supporting anti-British national movements, and for his editorial work against the colonial government. He entered the arena of national politics by supporting the Indian National Congress formed in 1885. As a supportive figure of the Muslim League, he created the opinions of the masses through his published newspaper, *Azad*. He joined the Khilafat and non-cooperation movements and was chosen as the secretary of the Khilafat committee at a Conference organized in 1920 at Ahsan Manzil of Dhaka. Great national leaders like Maulana Abul Kalam Azad (1885-1958), Maulana Mujibur Rahman, (1873-1924) and Maulana Maniruzzaman Islamabadi (1875-1950) were present at the conference. He had a conviction in the Hindu-Muslim brotherhood. In Calcutta in 1922, Akram Khan backed the Swaraj Party led by Chitta Ranjan Das. In 1923, he also backed the Bengal Pact. Sheikh Fazlul Karim, (1882-1936) from the district of Rangpur in Bangladesh was a Bengali poet and editor who attempted to preach the benefit of the Hindu-Muslim union during the imperial rule in India through the work of editing the journal, *Bashona*. Abul Kalam Shamsuddin (1897-1978) was a Bengali litterateur and journalist. He was also a part of the Indian non-cooperation and Khilafat movements. He worked as an editor of the daily newspaper, *Azad*. He was a believer in Mahatma Gandhi's ideology and he became a member of the Indian National Congress. The massacre of Jallianwala Bagh in 1919 in Amritsar, Punjab made this writer seriously alert about political intervention. He also joined the Muslim League in 1927. The writer, Syed Ameer Ali (1849-1928) was the first Bengali Muslim who completed post-graduation in History

and BL in 1869. He was also the first Muslim judge of the Kolkata High Court. He founded the Central National Mohamedan Association in 1878 to politically diagnose the Muslim problems in India and resolve them. Like Sir Syed Ahmad Khan(1817-1898), Ameer Ali broke with the Indian National Congress because they both thought that Muslims who were "tied to the wheels of the juggernaut of the majority" would eventually lose all sense of national identity (Subhans). However, unlike the Aligarh sage, Ameer Ali wanted Muslims to develop their unique political identity. In this connection, the author Amalendu De's comment can be quoted. He argued that in the colonial era, the mind of Muslims was largely "influenced simultaneously by a number of contradictory ideas, such as ideals of Islam, anti-colonialism, pan-Islamism, conservatism, liberalism, pro-British and anti-Congress attitudes" (448). Despite these, according to him, the friendly cooperation of Muslims and Hindus is essential for India to grow along contemporary lines. He urged his people to cooperate and live in harmony with all non-Muslims. As an educated Indian, he supported the hiring of Indians for higher positions in the state sector, the advancement of Indians into the Indian army, and the broader implementation of the concepts of local self-government (Subhans). He was blessed with the support of numerous non-Muslims. However, his initiative contributed to the Hindu-Muslim unity and the overall strength of Indians resulting in a helpful way to the independence of India. Pandit Reazuddin Ahamad Mashahdi(1819-1919) was a writer of *Samaj O Samskarak* (1889) and built strong relationship with Pandit Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar (1820-1891). His anti-British Bengali write-up in Sanskritized Bengali is highly renowned (as cited in De 450). He was deeply influenced by anti-imperialism and Pan-Islamism advocated by Sayyid Jamaluddin al-Afghani (1839-1897) who came to Calcutta in 1882. His book *Samaj O Samskarak* exposes the deeds of al-Afghani who preaches the anti-British feeling absorbed by a large portion of the Muslim elite. Unity between Muslims and Hindus was supported by Pandit Mashahdi. He also saw national unity as a way to free India from foreign rule and promote the well-being of the populace (as cited in De 452). Mohammad Mozammel Huq (860-1933) was a Muslim patriotic poet of Bengal. The British government seized his poems containing patriotic messages. He supported the idea of Hindu- Muslim tolerance similar to Mir

Mosharraf Hossain, he did not hold Hindus accountable for the deterioration and downfall of Muslims (as cited in De 457). Ismail Hossain Siraji (1880-1931) was a Muslim writer, leader, and orator from the Sirajganj district of Bengal. He was involved in varied parties and organizations like the Indian National Congress, Swarajya Party, Muslim League, Krishak samiti, Jamiut-e-Ulamay-i-Hind, and Anjuman-i-Ulama-i-Bangla. His imperative objective was to awaken the nation from slumber. The debut poetry collection by Siraji is titled *Anal Prabaha* (1899). The then-ruler of Britain confiscated this poetic work for its anti-government content and sentenced him to jail. He was a poet who wrote poems in support of national awakening and Indian Independence. Furthermore, to suppress his voice during oration and meetings, the British Government repeatedly imposed section 144. Sayed Emdad Ali (1875-1956) was a writer and editor of Bengal. He advocated that “India’s well-being depended on the Hindu-Muslim unity” (as cited in De 457). This ethos was “strengthened by a number of Muslim political leaders and activists during the *Swadeshi* and anti-partition agitation (1905-1911) as well as during the Khilafat and the non-cooperation movements (1919-1922)” (as cited in De 457). The writer, Rezaul Karim was one of the founding members of Muslim Sahitya Samaj (1926) in Dhaka. He believed in the ideology of a Hindu philosopher, Keshab Chandra Sen (1838-1884), who was a member of Brahma Samaj (1828), and who advocated the theory of harmonious relationship in all religions. He admired Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay for preaching Indian nationalism in his article “Bankim Chandrer *nikat Musalmaner Reen*” (Muslims’ debt to Bankim Chandra) in 1938. He argued that Muslim League’s objection to Bankim Chandra that he was against Muslim was not right. As a supporter of Indian National Congress he “firmly stood for united independent India” (as cited in De 460). Wazed Ali (1890-1951), a Bengali Muslim writer from the Hugli district held the view that fanaticism was incompatible with patriotism. He thought that provincial nationalism was the ground of nationalism in India. He also stressed the idea of Hindu-Muslim unity. Muzaffar Ahmed (1889-1973), was a communist politician and writer. At the outset, he “became friends with anti-colonial Urdu and Bangla Muslim political activists engaging with labor issues and organization of strikes by workers, which strengthened the ongoing Khilafat and

Non-Cooperation Movements” (Chattopadhyay). Then, he turned to the Marxist ideology and communist politics. “Dissemination of socialist literature and ideas was one of Muzaffar's principal aims. Since Muzaffar was part of the wider anti-colonial literary circle in Kolkata and had access to periodicals and journalists, he also managed to influence some radical anti-imperialist Bangla Muslim periodicals” (Chattopadhyay). He appeared “as a communist polemical writer in the second half of the 1920s mirrored a break from his earliest intellectual engagements” (Chattopadhyay). He was imprisoned for years due to his involvement in different movements and conspiracy cases by the British government.

Along with Muslim freedom fighters from Bengal, Bengali Muslim literary figures contributed to the Indian Independence. On one hand, their writings helped to arouse patriotic feelings and build Hindu-Muslim solidarity; on the other hand, they did their best through physical involvement in different national issues to root out the British government from India. Bengali Muslim female writers such as Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain and Razia Khatun Chaudhurani were not voiceless against the conspiracy of the colonial government. They endeavored to awaken Bengali Muslim women to strengthen the Indian resistance against the imperialist hegemony. Kaji Nazrul Islam influenced the Indians through his revolutionary poems. Mir Mosharruf Hossain made the Indians conscious of British tyranny, oppression, and exploitation. Other writers, Muhammad Shahidullah, Mohammad Akram Khan, Abul Kalam Shamsuddin, Ismail Hossain Siraji, Mohammad Mozammel Huq, Wazed Ali, Rezaul Karim, Muzaffar Ahmed, Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain, and Razia Khatun Chaudhurani played a historic role too in the Indian Independence.

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